

D3.6

A strategy report defining the connection of ENVRI in EOSC

Work Package	WP3
Lead partner	FMI
Status	Final
Deliverable type	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Due date	30 April 2023
Submission date	29 June 2023

Deliverable abstract

This strategy report provides a comprehensive understanding of the connection between European Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures and European Open Science Cloud. It aims to define and clarify the relationship between these two entities, highlighting the significance of their collaboration and integration. It focuses on participation in EOSC projects, integration with EOSC architecture, compliance with FAIR Principles, collaboration with EOSC Association, visibility and recognition of ENVRI within the EOSC ecosystem and capacity building and training.

DELIVERY SLIP

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DELIVERY LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V 0.1	15 May 2023	First version of the deliverable after survey analysis	Anca Hienola
V 0.2	24 June 2023	Second version of the deliverable after incorporation of comments from reviewers and WP3.	Anca Hienola
V 0.3	27 June 2023	Final version	Anca Hienola

DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D3.6 – A strategy report defining the connection of ENVRI in EOSC

1 Introduction

1.1 Background on ENVRI and EOSC

The science cluster of European Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) consist of Research Infrastructures (RIs) within the Environment Domain, as defined by ESFRI. These RIs encompass the four primary subdomains of the Earth system: Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth, and Biodiversity/Terrestrial Ecosystems. They serve as crucial providers of high-quality environmental research data and services in Europe, collected from distributed in-situ observing systems.

The ENVRI-FAIR project involves thirteen ENVRI and one data infrastructure – SeaDataNet –, aiming to develop a comprehensive set of FAIR data services for each participating RI. These services enhance the efficiency and productivity of researchers, support innovation, facilitate data- and knowledge-based decision-making, and establish a connection between the ENVRI Cluster and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The data services and products offered by ENVRI primarily target scientific communities and stakeholders at regional, national, and international scales. Most importantly, one of the objectives of ENVRI-FAIR is that all the standards, services and policies developed during the lifetime of the project are shared with the wider ENVRI community and are compliant with strategic partnerships and collaborators in EOSC. In this context, ENVRI-FAIR represents not only mature research infrastructures on the ESFRI road but includes also those RIs which are evolving and maturing. This representation is probably best delineated within the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures (also known as BEERi) where ENVRI-FAIR's activities are presented and decisions concerning strategy, vision and collaboration are made accordingly. By its very nature ENVRI-FAIR bares a significant strategic value for the entire community and serves as a channel towards the national, European, and international stakeholders and initiatives.

EOSC is a long-term joint European effort tackling a federated ecosystem for research data and services in Europe. It seeks to facilitate seamless access, sharing, and reuse of research data, enabling scientists and researchers to collaborate more effectively across disciplines and borders.

The ENVRI and EOSC nexus involves integrating the environmental research infrastructures and the connected scientific communities into the EOSC framework. This integration ensures that the data, services, and resources provided by ENVRI are made accessible through the EOSC platform, alongside other research disciplines. By connecting ENVRI to EOSC, researchers gain broader access to environmental data and services, enabling interdisciplinary collaborations and fostering the advancement of environmental research.

The collaboration between ENVRI and EOSC also promotes the adoption of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles. It aims to develop FAIR data services within ENVRI, making environmental research data more discoverable, accessible, and reusable across the research community. This connection enables ENVRI to contribute to the overarching goals of EOSC, including facilitating open science, enhancing data interoperability, and promoting cross-disciplinary research collaborations.

As such, the relationship between ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC is a strategic partnership that leverages the strengths of both initiatives to advance environmental research, foster collaboration, and promote open data and science.

1.2 Purpose of the Strategy Report

The purpose of this strategy report is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the connection between European Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It aims to define and clarify the relationship between these two entities, highlighting the significance of their collaboration and integration.

The strategy focuses on several key aspects:

- **Participation in EOSC Projects:** ENVRI-FAIR actively sought involvement in various EOSC projects and initiatives. By participating in these projects, ENVRI-FAIR aimed to contribute its expertise, data, and services to the EOSC ecosystem. This strategy allowed ENVRI to align its activities with the broader goals and objectives of EOSC while promoting collaboration and knowledge exchange.
- **Integration with EOSC Architecture:** ENVRI-FAIR focused on ensuring the seamless integration of ENVRI data services and resources within the EOSC architecture. This involved aligning ENVRI's data infrastructure, standards, and protocols with the EOSC framework to facilitate interoperability and data accessibility.
- **Compliance with FAIR Principles:** The strategy emphasised the adoption and implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles across ENVRI-FAIR. By making ENVRI data and services FAIR-compliant, the project aimed to enhance the discoverability and usability of environmental research data within EOSC, promoting open science practices.
- **Collaboration with EOSC Association:** ENVRI-FAIR actively engaged with EOSC Task Forces and initiatives to foster collaboration and share best practices. This collaboration aimed to contribute to the development of EOSC policies, guidelines, and technical frameworks, ensuring that ENVRI's requirements and perspectives were considered in the overall EOSC implementation.
- **Visibility and recognition of ENVRI within the EOSC ecosystem:** Encourage collaboration and partnerships with relevant stakeholders, organisations, and initiatives within EOSC to amplify the visibility of ENVRI. This involves establishing mutually beneficial relationships, engaging in joint activities, and leveraging networks to enhance the reach and impact of ENVRI's visibility promotion initiatives.
- **Capacity Building and Training:** The strategy recognised the importance of capacity building and training activities to enable ENVRI stakeholders to effectively participate in EOSC. This included providing training on EOSC tools, standards, and data management practices, empowering ENVRI researchers and infrastructure operators to maximise their engagement with EOSC.

From the outset, the strategy related to EOSC in ENVRI-FAIR focused on promoting integration, collaboration, and alignment with EOSC objectives. By actively participating in EOSC projects, aligning with EOSC architecture, complying with FAIR principles, collaborating with EOSC Task Forces, and investing in capacity building, ENVRI-FAIR aimed to enhance its connection with EOSC and contribute to the development of a robust and accessible European open science infrastructure.

2 ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC: understanding the relationship

2.1 Alignment of Goals and Objectives

The harmonisation of goals and objectives between ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC forms a strong foundation for their collaboration and integration. Both initiatives share a common vision of advancing open science principles, promoting data accessibility, and fostering innovation within the European research landscape.

ENVRI-FAIR's goals revolved around providing high-quality environmental research data and services to scientific communities, stakeholders, and policymakers. By integrating with EOSC, ENVRI-FAIR aimed to enhance the discoverability, interoperability, and reusability of its data and services, making them more accessible to researchers across different scientific disciplines.

EOSC, on the other hand, aims to create a federated and user-centric infrastructure that fosters collaboration, data sharing, and the adoption of open science practices. By facilitating seamless access to research outputs, resources, and tools, EOSC aims to break down barriers and promote interdisciplinary collaboration. EOSC recognises the value of diverse scientific domains, including the environmental field, and seeks to integrate and harmonise their data and services within a single ecosystem.

The goals of both ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC converge on several key aspects. Firstly, they aim to enable open and transparent access to research data, empowering researchers to build upon existing knowledge and drive scientific advancements. Both initiatives emphasise the importance of data interoperability, aiming to establish common standards and protocols that facilitate the integration of diverse data sources. Additionally, they recognise the need for collaboration and knowledge sharing, encouraging researchers to work across disciplinary boundaries to address complex environmental challenges.

By aligning their goals and objectives, ENVRI and EOSC create a synergy that amplifies the impact of their individual efforts. ENVRI's participation in EOSC strengthens the environmental research capabilities within the broader EOSC framework, enriching the available data and expertise. This integration enhances the interdisciplinary nature of EOSC, enabling researchers to explore connections and collaborations with environmental scientists and utilise environmental data in their respective domains. Similarly, ENVRI benefits from the technical infrastructure and tools provided by EOSC, facilitating the integration of its data and services into a larger ecosystem.

2.2 Importance of Collaboration and Integration

Collaboration and integration between ENVRI and EOSC are crucial for achieving their shared goals. By collaborating, both initiatives can leverage each other's strengths, resources, and expertise, resulting in a more robust and comprehensive research ecosystem.

Through integration, ENVRI can benefit from the technical infrastructure, tools, and services offered by EOSC. This integration enables ENVRI to align its data management practices, standards, and protocols with EOSC's guidelines, ensuring compatibility and interoperability with other scientific domains. Additionally, integration with EOSC facilitates the seamless access and discovery of ENVRI data and services, making them more accessible to researchers and stakeholders across disciplines.

For EOSC, the collaboration with ENVRI strengthens its environmental research capabilities, enriching the range of available data and services. ENVRI's involvement expands the scope and depth of research possibilities within EOSC, fostering collaboration among researchers from diverse scientific backgrounds. This integration enhances the overall research potential of EOSC and contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the environmental and Earth system sciences.

2.3 Benefits of ENVRI's Involvement in EOSC

ENVRI's active involvement in EOSC brings forth numerous benefits to both initiatives and the broader scientific community. These benefits span across various aspects and contribute to advancing open science, enabling data-driven research, and fostering collaboration. Here are some of the key benefits:

1. **Enhanced Data Accessibility and Discoverability:** By participating in EOSC, ENVRI gains access to a broader user base, expanding the reach and impact of its environmental research data and services. Integration with EOSC enhances the discoverability of ENVRI resources, making them more easily accessible to researchers across different scientific domains. This increased accessibility fosters interdisciplinary collaborations, allowing researchers to leverage ENVRI's valuable data and insights for their studies.
2. **Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Innovation:** ENVRI's involvement in EOSC promotes interdisciplinary collaboration by bridging the gap between environmental sciences and other scientific disciplines. This collaboration sparks new insights, ideas, and innovative approaches to addressing complex environmental challenges. Researchers from diverse domains can leverage ENVRI's rich dataset to explore connections, discover new research avenues, and drive advancements in environmental and Earth system sciences.
3. **Broader Impact and Societal Relevance:** Through EOSC, ENVRI can amplify the impact and societal relevance of its research and services. The integration of ENVRI data into the EOSC ecosystem ensures that environmental research outcomes reach a wider audience, including policymakers, stakeholders, and the general public. This broader impact facilitates evidence-based decision-making, supports sustainable development, and addresses pressing environmental issues at regional, national, and international scales.
4. **Harmonisation and Standardisation:** Participation in EOSC encourages ENVRI to align its data management practices, standards, and protocols with the broader European and international scientific communities. This harmonisation and standardisation improve interoperability and compatibility between ENVRI and other research infrastructures, enabling seamless data

exchange, integration, and collaboration. By adhering to common standards, ENVRI enhances the quality, reliability, and reusability of its data, making it valuable for a wider range of research purposes.

5. **Access to Technical Infrastructure and Services:** ENVRI's involvement in EOSC grants access to the technical infrastructure, services, and tools provided by EOSC. This access enables ENVRI to leverage state-of-the-art technologies, data management systems, and computing resources. By utilising these resources, ENVRI can enhance the efficiency, scalability, and effectiveness of its data services, empowering researchers with robust and reliable infrastructure to conduct cutting-edge research.
6. **Opportunities for Funding and Collaboration:** Through its integration with EOSC, ENVRI opens doors to potential funding opportunities and collaborative projects. Participation in EOSC flagship initiatives, calls for proposals, and collaborative networks can provide ENVRI with access to additional resources, expertise, and partnerships. These opportunities further strengthen ENVRI's position as a key player in the European research landscape and enable it to contribute to addressing global environmental challenges.

The expectations of the ENVRI community from EOSC have been expressed through a position paper (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3666806>) published in February 2020. That paper states that ENVRI-FAIR supports the idea of the EOSC and its services being a public good, emphasising the need for long-term and sustained funding to ensure its continued operation. The Federating Core, including the Compliance Framework, Hub Portfolio, and Shared Resources, is seen as the central component of the EOSC, while research data curation remains the responsibility of the contributing research infrastructures. ENVRI-FAIR believes that the Federating Core and Shared Resources can be integrated into the operation models of ENVRI Research Infrastructures if sustainability and access issues are addressed. The ENVRI's play a crucial role in the EOSC as providers of data and various services, as well as being the primary users of EOSC services. The relationship between funding for research infrastructures and EOSC-derived funding needs to be detailed, along with clear specifications of services and resources for each facility.

The ENVRI-FAIR cluster project expects EOSC to provide added value to the research community by enhancing the findability and accessibility of research data and services, offering platforms for virtual research environments, supporting resource integration, and ensuring sustainability through long-term funding. The cluster project on the other hand, can contribute its domain-specific knowledge, FAIR-based tools, and the ENVRI-Hub to the EOSC ecosystem.

3 Defining the connection – key areas of engagement

ENVRI-FAIR recognised that, to successfully navigate its path towards fully integrating with EOSC, it could not operate as a secluded entity. The journey to EOSC required forging strong collaborations, establishing partnerships, and actively engaging with key players in the EOSC arena. ENVRI-FAIR

understood the significance of building bridges and working in synergy with other stakeholders to collectively shape the future of open science (Figure 1).

One of the primary ways ENVRI-FAIR ensured its integration into the EOSC landscape was by actively participating in EOSC governance structures. By taking an active role in

EOSC governance, ENVRI-FAIR contributed to the decision-making processes, shaping the direction, policies, and strategies of EOSC. This

Figure 1 ENVRI-FAIR roadmap towards implementation of EOSC

involvement enabled ENVRI-FAIR to voice its perspectives, advocate for the needs and interests of the environmental research infrastructures and ensure their seamless integration within EOSC.

In addition to governance, ENVRI-FAIR took part in the coordination and participation of EOSC-related projects. These projects provide a platform for collaboration, knowledge exchange, and the development of innovative solutions that further enhance the integration of ENVRI within EOSC. By actively engaging in such projects, ENVRI-FAIR was able to contribute its expertise, share best practices, and align its activities with the broader EOSC objectives.

ENVRI-FAIR also recognised the importance of collaborating with other science clusters and data communities. By fostering close collaborations with these entities, ENVRI-FAIR could tap into their expertise, leverage synergies, and collectively address common challenges. Through these collaborations, ENVRI-FAIR established strong networks, shared resources, and explored opportunities for joint initiatives that promote the integration of environmental research infrastructures within the broader EOSC ecosystem.

By actively engaging with EOSC governance, coordinating, and participating in EOSC-related projects, and collaborating with other science clusters and data communities, ENVRI-FAIR ensured its extensive and dynamic involvement within the EOSC ecosystem.

3.1 Engaging with EOSC Association

To actively contribute to the realisation and effective implementation of EOSC, ENVRI-FAIR participants responded to the call for the integration of members into the designated EOSC-Association Advisory Groups. There are five Advisory Groups focusing on overarching themes that are important for the realisation of EOSC which consist of Task Forces with members working on specific topics related to each of the Advisory Groups. Four Task Forces within three advisory groups, served as platforms for leveraging the experience and expertise of ENVRI-FAIR members. They play a pivotal role in formulating strategic options, developing plans, and providing insights for the successful implementation of EOSC.

The participation of ENVRI-FAIR members in these Task Forces enabled them to actively shape and influence the development of EOSC. Drawing upon their diverse backgrounds and understanding of the environmental research infrastructures, members collaborated with other stakeholders to define the strategic priorities and actions required to advance EOSC's objectives. By actively engaging in discussions and sharing best practices, members collectively worked towards developing innovative approaches and solutions that align with the overall vision of EOSC.

The following task forces have benefitted from ENVRI-FAIR experts:

- i. **The PID Policy and Implementation Task Force (PID TF)** aims to address gaps in the PID ecosystem mentioned in the current SRIA version. Its goals include highlighting mature PID infrastructures, standardising the PID graph, integrating PIDs into FAIR data management, and addressing PIDs and sensitive data. The task force provides recommendations on PID management and establish certification criteria.
- ii. **The Semantic Interoperability Task Force** aims to enhance the EOSC Interoperability Framework by advancing and implementing semantic interoperability recommendations. This involves focusing on metadata standards and providing guidance on how to effectively align and match semantic artifacts through crosswalks. The task force will facilitate workshops and hackathons to explore real-life examples and foster the exchange of knowledge.
- iii. **The Data Stewardship, Curricula, and Career Paths Task Force** focuses on the role of Data Stewards and their responsibilities. It collaborates with various stakeholders, consolidates insights and recommendations, and develops a minimal curriculum and career paths for data stewards.
- iv. **The Technical Interoperability of Data and Services Task Force** uses the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF) recommendations on technical architecture as a basis to enhance the EOSC Core and Exchange outlined in the SRIA. The task force produced important documents, such as first principles document and a landscape overview of the EIF. It will also provide technical architecture descriptions of the EIF, including examples of adaptation hints for major existing solutions.

The inclusion of ENVRI-FAIR participants in the Task Forces not only highlights their commitment to EOSC but also reinforces the significance of their expertise and contributions in shaping the future of open science.

3.2 Participation in EOSC Future

The EOSC-Future project is the flagship EOSC project aimed at advancing the development and implementation of EOSC by addressing key challenges and opportunities through collaboration among various stakeholders, including researchers, service providers, and policymakers. EOSC Future builds on the existing baseline for the European Open Science Cloud to deliver a platform with a durable set of user-friendly components that are designed for the long haul.

EOSC Future has been an essential endeavour for ENVRI-FAIR, as it concentrated our efforts since the inception of the EOSC-Future project towards shaping the future of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). ENVRI-FAIR had a strong presence in various work packages within the project, demonstrating our commitment to actively contribute and collaborate.

In the **Strategic and Oversight Board (SOB)**, ENVRI-FAIR is well represented by the coordinator of both ENVRI-FAIR project and **IAGOS AISBL**. This dual role brings valuable expertise and

leadership to the board, ensuring that our interests, goals, and perspectives are effectively communicated and advocated for at the strategic level.

In **WP3 (Architecture and Interoperability)**, The ENVRI-FAIR involvement is extensive, with **EPOS ERIC** participating in all tasks. EPOS actively engaged in discussions regarding the

Interoperability Framework and contribute to the establishment of a Working Group on Metadata. This ensured that the specific requirements of the ENVRI-FAIR cluster are considered in the development of EOSC architecture.

WP5 (Design and development of the portal demand layer) is another crucial area where **ICOS ERIC** and **MARIS** are dedicated to making the EOSC Portal user-friendly and aligned with the needs and perspectives of users. Following the motto of

"vox populi," the participants prioritised user feedback and strove to enhance the overall user experience. Task 5.1 is led by ICOS.

Within **WP6 (Integration of the community services and products into EOSC - led by LifeWatch ERIC)**, ENVRI-FAIR has been involved in the development of three Test Science projects:

Climate Change Impact on Biodiversity and Ecosystems in Europe

This science project focuses on investigating the increase of non-indigenous and invasive species (NIS) in European ecosystems, which can have significant impacts on biodiversity and socio-economic systems. It aims to integrate various scientific disciplines, such as genomics, biodiversity, and socioeconomics, into an analytical framework to better understand the effects of NIS. The project also aims to connect this framework with relevant data infrastructures on the EOSC platform, enabling collaboration and access to large datasets. Partners include **LifeWatch ERIC, MARIS, OGS, ICOS ERIC, IFREMER, EMSO ERIC, NOC-BODC, EMBRC ERIC, VLIZ, HMRC, and UGOT**. The project seeks to demonstrate the benefits of web-based science and promote the use of EOSC for research in this field.

State of the environment

This science project aims to develop a user-friendly dashboard with real-time environmental indicators to inform the public and policymakers about the state of the environment. The dashboard will be integrated into the ENVRI-Hub, a virtual platform for ENVRI-FAIR data and services, which will be part of the EOSC platform. The project will establish analytical workflows for different environmental disciplines and connect them to the EOSC platform through the ENVRI-Hub. The project also aims to showcase the advantages of web-based science using EOSC. Partners in this project include EOSC LifeWatch ERIC, MARIS, and ICOS ERIC.

Climate-neutral and smart cities

This project brings together resources from two Science Clusters: ENVRI-FAIR and SSHOC. As part of the SSHOC consortium, the European Social Survey (ESS) collects data on various topics, such as

political and social trust, health, attitudes towards climate change and energy, democracy, and digital communication.

The project aims to prepare the tool for integration into the EOSC and foster interdisciplinary research. The tool will be upgraded to complement ESS's individual-level data with data from other clusters, including health, environment, democracy, civil society, and gender. A case study will be conducted by SSHOC and ENVRI FAIR to showcase the interdisciplinary opportunities provided by this resource. The tool will play a crucial role in the EOSC catalogue, promoting interoperability and connectivity between science clusters, the Smart Cities marketplace, and EOSC.

Partners in this project include SSHOC (ESS ERIC, CESSDA ERIC) and ENVRI-FAIR (IAGOS AISBL through in-kind contribution).

WP9 Training & skills

ICOS ERIC is actively involved in **WP9 (Training and Skills)**, where it contributes by providing training packages for both users and providers. ENVRI-FAIR recognises the importance of equipping stakeholders with the necessary

knowledge and skills to effectively utilise and contribute to the EOSC ecosystem.

WP10 Stakeholder engagement, outreach and marketing

Furthermore, **ICOS ERIC** plays a significant role in **WP10 (Stakeholder engagement, outreach, and marketing)**, ensuring a strong connection between EOSC Future and the scientific community and other stakeholders involved in

EOSC. This collaboration bridges the gap between the project and the broader scientific community, fostering meaningful engagement and knowledge exchange.

It is worth noting that our active engagement across these different work packages has significantly increased the visibility of ENVRI-FAIR beyond the environmental sciences domain. Our diverse and substantial contributions to the development of EOSC showcase the significance of our involvement and highlight the broader impact we have in shaping the future of open science and FAIR data practices.

3.3 Participation in other EOSC Projects

ENVRI-FAIR actively participated in various projects within the EOSC family, either through individual involvement or as a representation of research infrastructures (RIs). Here are a few examples:

1. **BLUE Cloud:** ENVRI-FAIR contributes to the BLUE Cloud project, which focuses on providing services for the discovery and access of marine data. Within this project, ENVRI-FAIR's partner MARIS collaborated to offer data discovery and access services. Additionally, two of the nine "Blue data infrastructures," namely ICOS and Argo, were part of the project. They contributed their expertise in data management and provided services related to marine data discovery and access. Euro-Argo, another member of ENVRI-FAIR, explored the use of machine learning techniques for assessing data quality of the collected Argo floaters data, indicating the consortium's interest in advancing data analysis methods.

2. **EOSC-ENHANCE:** This two-year project aimed to enhance the functionality of the EOSC Portal and improve the catalogue of services while connecting thematic data clouds. ICOS, one of the project partners of ENVRI-FAIR, actively contributed to this initiative. Among various developments within the EOSC Portal, ICOS provided input for the onboarding implementations, which facilitated the integration of services and datasets into the portal.

3. **EOSC-Nordic:** the project focused on facilitating the coordination of EOSC-related initiatives within the Nordic and Baltic countries. While ENVRI-FAIR itself is not directly involved through an RI partner, individual participation from ENVRI members took place in the project's Work Package 2 (Policies, Legal Issues, and Sustainability). This work package fundamentally focused on policy-oriented aspects, engaging national policymakers and funders to ensure the long-term sustainability and support for the EOSC infrastructure.

Contribution as Use Cases: Several ENVRI-FAIR RIs, including ICOS, ACTRIS, and SIOS, have been recognised as "use cases" or good examples for their policies and sustainability strategies within the EOSC Nordic project. These RIs served as valuable references in terms of implementing effective policies and sustainable practices. ENVRI-FAIR's involvement in this capacity showcases the consortium's expertise and its commitment to sharing best practices with the wider EOSC community.

4. **FAIRsFAIR:** the project focused on the development of a knowledge infrastructure for quality data management, emphasising development procedures, standards, metrics, and related matters based on the FAIR principles. ENVRI-FAIR members contributed to the FAIRsFAIR policy work package at an individual level, particularly in developing policy tools such as the ACME maturity model for research performing organisations. This participation further facilitated convergence in policy development efforts, strengthening ENVRI-FAIR's dedication to advancing the adoption of open and FAIR data principles.

3.4 Engagement with RDA

The ENVRI community participants actively collaborate with various standards and recommendation organisations, ranging from ISO and W3C to RDA (Research Data Alliance). Within the RDA, ENVRI-FAIR engages extensively by chairing and co-chairing working groups or interest groups. Some of these groups include:

1. **Metadata Standard Catalogue Working Group:** This group focuses on developing and maintaining a comprehensive catalogue of metadata standards relevant to the ENVRI community.

2. **Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology Working Group (I-ADOPT WG):** The I-ADOPT WG works towards establishing interoperable and standardised descriptions of observable properties, ensuring consistent data representation across environmental research infrastructures.

3. **Metadata Interest Group:** The Metadata Interest Group explores best practices, guidelines, and advancements in metadata management, promoting interoperability and discoverability of environmental research data.

4. **ESIP/RDA Earth, Space and Environmental Sciences Interest Group:** This joint interest group between ESIP (Earth Science Information Partners) and RDA focuses on addressing challenges and promoting collaboration in earth, space, and environmental sciences.

5. **Virtual Research Environments Interest Group:** This group explores the development and utilisation of virtual research environments, which provide collaborative platforms for researchers to access, analyse, and share data within the ENVRI community.

Additionally, ENVRI-FAIR organised side events related to ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC topics, creating opportunities for discussions, presentations, panel debates, and active participation. These engagements contribute to the exchange of knowledge, the advancement of standards, and the promotion of open and FAIR practices within the environmental research community.

3.5 Science Clusters collaboration

Five science clusters bringing together the research infrastructures within a specific domain of Astronomy and Particle Physics (ESCAPE¹), Environmental Sciences ENVRI-FAIR², Life Sciences (EOSC-Life³), Neutron and Light Sources (PANOSC⁴), and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSHOC⁵)

Figure 2: Clusters' expectations, needs, and contributions converge, resulting in a unified perspective on the EOSC's role and purpose

have united to strengthen Europe's scientific instruments and research infrastructures, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration to address critical global challenges. The Science Clusters play a crucial role in the development and implementation of the EOSC, making structural cooperation among them a natural choice. To facilitate coordination and collaboration, regular bi-weekly virtual meetings have been held among the cluster projects. These meetings have focused on strategic aspects and sustainability, particularly within the context of EOSC. By coming together, the clusters have been able to harmonise their responses to EOSC-related requests and collectively engage with the EOSC Association. Their strong representation in the EOSC FUTURE

project has further strengthened their collaboration and ensured effective alignment with EOSC objectives.

The clusters' expectations, needs, and contributions converge, resulting in a unified perspective on the EOSC's role and purpose. At the core of this unified perspective is the recognition that the EOSC is conceptualised as consisting of three levels: E-Infrastructure consolidation, Open science, and Scientific Communities' content and users (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**).

For a comprehensive elucidation of the collaborative endeavours within the cluster, we direct the reader's attention to Deliverable 1.8, where an intricately detailed depiction of the cluster collaboration can be found.

3.6 Integration with EOSC architecture

It might be illustrative to see the important position of ENVRI-FAIR within the EOSC fabric by enabling the RIs services and data access inside and outside the typical user communities through ENVRI-Hub which is the central gateway through which ENVRI community shares its FAIRness experience, technologies, and training as well as research products and connects to EOSC, and to put science at the heart of EOSC, by helping EOSC to open up new scientific perspectives for researchers (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**).

To ensure interoperability, ENVRI-FAIR adopts a technology-driven approach based on the FAIR principles. Two key aspects are identified: **metadata** and a **web-service based approach**.

The ENVRI-FAIR project and the Environmental Research Infrastructures within the ENVRI Science Cluster aim to achieve interoperability within the framework of the EOSC architecture, as it is considered crucial for enabling seamless access, sharing, and reusability of data and digital assets across different RIs and scientific domains.

For **metadata**, ENVRI-FAIR recognises the need for a comprehensive metadata schema that can accommodate the heterogeneity of existing metadata standards used by different RIs. This schema should

¹ <https://projectescape.eu/>

² <https://envri.eu/>

³ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

⁴ <https://www.panosc.eu/>

⁵ <https://sshopencloud.eu/>

enable the representation of various information related to resources, publications, individuals, organisations, facilities, equipment, and more, in a machine-readable and machine-understandable format. The goal is to provide a consistent and standardised way of describing datasets and digital assets across the ENVRI RIs.

Figure 3: EOSC architecture

The **web-service based approach** focuses on enabling users, both humans and machines, to access datasets and digital assets through web services. These services should not only provide access to data but also offer functionalities associated with the datasets, such as search capabilities and appropriate authentication mechanisms. By utilising web services, ENVRI-FAIR aims to ensure true machine readability and actionability of the data.

To facilitate interoperability and access to ENVRI RIs' digital assets, the ENVRI Catalogue of Services, based on the CERIF standard, plays a central role. This rich metadata catalogue stores detailed information about services and other digital assets across the participating RIs. The ENVRI Catalogue of Services is designed to be compatible with the evolving EOSC metadata standards. By converting the ENVRI-FAIR Catalogue of Services metadata to EOSC standards, the EOSC can access comprehensive information about the ENVRI RIs and their digital assets.

The ENVRI-FAIR project also leverages the ENVRI-Hub platform, which acts as a central hub for discovery, documentation, and access to services and digital assets. ENVRI-Hub provides standardised interfaces, machine-actionability, and user support within the EOSC context. The aim is to ensure that ENVRI RIs are ready to onboard the EOSC when the EOSC metadata standards are sufficient to manage the technical and governance aspects of accessing ENVRI RIs' digital assets, including licensing, authorisation, citation/acknowledgment, and metadata richness for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse.

Although the complete details of the EOSC architecture are not completely defined, the approach adopted by ENVRI-FAIR, initially implemented by the EPOS ERIC and later expanded to other RIs within ENVRI, proves to be the most flexible. This approach can accommodate different architectures and federation types, providing the necessary information for the EOSC to interact with the domain-specific RIs' nodes. As a first step, EPOS and LifeWatch RIs have gradually mapped their catalogues to the evolving EOSC catalogues, ensuring ENVRI's readiness for onboarding to EOSC.